

CULTURAL LEADERSHIP GEARING TOWARDS HISTORICAL RECOLLECTION

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ABSTRACT

This study delves into cultural leadership in education, emphasizing educators' vital role in fostering appreciation for history and culture. However, challenges such as the scarcity of relevant references impede effective implementation. It aims to assess cultural leadership among teachers at Mercedes Elementary School, investigate resource integration for local history teaching, identify challenges in contextualizing history, explore the link between cultural leadership and resource integration, and propose strategies for enhancing teachers' cultural leadership in Mercedes, Camarines Norte. Using quantitative descriptive correlational research design with 54 respondents, the findings indicate a high level of cultural leadership among teachers at Mercedes Elementary School, with an overall weighted mean of 3.18. Additionally, the integration of educational materials for teaching local history in Mercedes, Camarines Norte, was found to be high, with a weighted mean of 3.10. Primary challenges faced by teachers include time constraints, limited access to technology, insufficient community involvement, lack of training opportunities, inadequate funding, difficulty accessing historical resources, incorporation of local narratives, multimedia creation, collaboration with local artists, and establishing a centralized digital repository. Moreover, a significant relationship exists between teachers' cultural leadership and the integration of educational materials. The study proposes Digital Instructional Material that represents a significant step toward enhancing the cultural leadership skills of teachers in Mercedes, Camarines Norte. By providing comprehensive support and intervention, the Digital Instructional Material

equips educators with the necessary tools to integrate local history and culture into their teaching practices effectively.

Keywords: *Cultural leadership, local history teaching, historical recollection, curriculum integration*

INTRODUCTION

Cultural leadership in the realm of education revolves around the proactive role educators play in fostering an appreciation for history and culture among their learners. This encompasses the initiative, and skills teachers employ to convey local history and culture, enabling learners to develop a profound understanding of their roots and the context they inhabit. The Local Government Code of 1991 (Republic Act No. 7160), which explicitly underscores the imperative of nurturing an appreciation for local history and culture acknowledges the pivotal function it serves in shaping the collective consciousness of learners and their connection to their locality. Research by Suryani et al. (2020) highlights how teachers are uniquely positioned to take initiatives in this regard, bridging the gap between the legal mandate and its practical execution. In the study by Ledesma (2020), she pointed out that teachers' ability to convey local history and culture effectively hinges on their cultural leadership – the initiative and skills they demonstrate in this endeavor. However, the effective implementation of this educational mandate faces a substantial challenge – the scarcity of accessible and relevant references. In Mercedes, Camarines Norte. This issue is not unique and reflects a broader challenge in local history education, as noted in the study by Sanchez (2019), where educators frequently confront the limited availability of resources customized to their particular locality. Teachers, in their capacity as cultural leaders, need to be proactive in identifying alternative solutions and methodologies to ensure that historical recollection remains an integral part of the learning experience.

Recognizing the importance of empowering teachers in their cultural leadership roles, interventions can be designed to enhance their skills. Educational materials and support systems can be developed to provide teachers with the tools needed to effectively convey local history and culture. This study will serve as a valuable foundation for developing strategies that align closely with the unique circumstances of the local educational interventions, ensuring the effectiveness and sustainability of cultural leadership empowerment initiatives and consequently improving historical recollections in the schools in Mercedes, Camarines Norte.

Research Questions

The purpose of this research is to assess and enhance cultural leadership among teachers at Mercedes Elementary School, Mercedes, Camarines Norte, Philippines by assessing current levels, analyzing available educational resources for local history, understanding challenges in contextualizing lessons, and material development. More precisely, the present study sought to investigate the subsequent inquiries:

1. What is the current level of cultural leadership among teachers at Mercedes Elementary School, in terms of:
 - 1.1 instructional practices;
 - 1.2 curricular integration;
 - 1.3 assessments techniques; and
 - 1.4 resource acquisition?
2. What is the level of integration of the available educational materials and resources for teaching the local history of Mercedes, Camarines Norte?
3. What specific challenges do teachers face when localizing and contextualizing the history of Mercedes, Camarines Norte in their lessons?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the current level of cultural leadership of teachers and the level of integration of educational materials and resources for teaching the local history of Mercedes, Camarines Norte?
5. What intervention may be proposed in enhancing the cultural leadership skills of teachers in Mercedes, Camarines Norte?

METHODOLOGY

This study focused on evaluating the cultural leadership skills of teachers at Mercedes Elementary School in Mercedes, Camarines Norte, Philippines during the third quarter of the 2023-2024 school year. The study involved the teachers at Mercedes Elementary School as respondents, focusing on examining the variables of Cultural Leadership Gearing and Historical Recollection. The study employed a quantitative approach to obtain data on cultural leadership and historical recollection. Data analysis methods encompass using Likert scale-based questionnaires, and checklist questionnaires. These techniques were employed to assess the present state of cultural leadership, ascertain the accessibility of educational resources, comprehend the difficulties in adapting history lessons to the context, and establish the requirements and preferences of teachers to determine their cultural leadership abilities.

The scope of this study was delimited to 54 teachers of Mercedes Elementary School in Mercedes, Camarines Norte, Philippines hence constraining the applicability of the findings to this particular educational setting. The period was limited to the third quarter of the 2023-2024 academic year. The research primarily examined teachers as participants and did not encompass other stakeholders. Furthermore, the focus was limited to cultural leadership specifically about historical recollection, excluding broader aspects of cultural leadership that may exist in other domains. The establishment of these boundaries is crucial to uphold the concentration and significance of the investigation within the set bounds.

This study utilized quantitative method using Descriptive-Correlational design. The descriptive component focused on exploring the current state of cultural leadership among teachers, encompassing instructional practices, curricular integration, assessment techniques, and resource acquisition. It extends this descriptive approach to assess the level of integration of educational materials and resources for teaching local

history. The correlational aspect examined the potential relationships between the current level of cultural leadership among teachers and the integration of educational materials for history instruction. The study had 54 Araling Panlipunan teachers as respondents in Mercedes Elementary School and used total enumeration as the sampling technique. To determine the current level of cultural leadership among teachers at Mercedes Elementary School, weighted mean was used. The variables such as instructional practices, curricular integration, assessment techniques, and resource acquisition. Further, in the integration of educational materials for teaching local history also used weighted mean. SOP 1 and 2 were treated using the weighted mean method.

Specific challenges faced by teachers, SOP 3 were explored using frequency and ranking. SOP 4 or the core of the study involved examining the relationship between the current level of cultural leadership and the integration of educational materials, using correlation analysis, potentially employing Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (r). This analysis aimed to determine the strength and direction of the correlation, offering insights into the interconnectedness of these variables.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1

Current Level of Cultural Leadership among Teachers at Mercedes Elementary School in terms of Instructional Practices

Instructional Practices	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
I seamlessly incorporate local historical narratives of Mercedes, and Camarines Norte into my lesson plans.	3.22	High Level
I actively involve students in discussions that promote cultural understanding and appreciation of Mercedes, Camarines Norte.	3.57	Extremely High Level
I exhibit sensitivity to the historical and cultural backgrounds of my Mercedeseño students during instruction.	3.35	Extremely High Level
I encourage students to explore and express their cultural identities as Mercedeseños within the classroom environment.	3.33	Extremely High Level
I implement creative approaches to make learning of the local history and culture more engaging and impactful for students.	3.25	Extremely High Level

Overall Weighted Mean

3.34

Extremely High Level

Rating Scale	Descriptive Interpretation
3.25 – 4.00	Extremely High Level
2.50 – 3.24	High Level
1.75 – 2.49	Low Level
1.00 – 1.74	Extremely Low Level

The Current Level of Cultural Leadership among Teachers at Mercedes Elementary School in terms of Instructional Practices is extremely high level with an average weighted mean of 3.34 while the sub-indicator concerning in incorporating local historical narratives into lesson plans had the least weighted mean of 3.22 interpreted as high level. This indicates a strong commitment to promoting cultural understanding and appreciation among learners. However, the slightly lower weighted mean for incorporating local historical narratives into lesson plans highlights the need for teachers to further integrate local context into their teaching materials and curriculum.

The result highlights how teachers can enrich the learning environment and deepen students' connection to their local heritage. The implications point to the importance of building on the school's existing practices to foster a stronger appreciation of cultural identity, ensuring that learners not only engage with cultural content but also internalize the significance of their local history.

Desinguraj and Kumar (2021) study on innovative teaching methods in history supports these implications by demonstrating how creative approaches in teaching can effectively convey cultural and historical content. Similarly, Amores (2015) exploration of tracing local history through object biography aligns with the implications by emphasizing the role of tangible artifacts in fostering a deeper connection to local culture.

Table 2

Current Level of Cultural Leadership among Teachers at Mercedes Elementary School in Terms of Curricular Integration

Curricular Integration	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
I actively incorporate local cultural themes and perspectives into the curriculum across different subjects.	3.27	Extremely High Level
I ensure that lessons reflect the diversity of students' backgrounds and experiences, including those from Mercedes, Camarines Norte.	3.42	Extremely High Level
I adapt teaching materials and resources to include authentic representations of local culture and heritage.	3.33	Extremely High Level

I collaborate with colleagues to develop interdisciplinary projects that emphasize cultural relevance and integration.	3.14	High Level
I regularly assess and adjust curriculum plans to better incorporate and celebrate the cultural identities of my students.	3.20	High Level
Overall Weighted Mean	3.27	Extremely High Level
Rating Scale	Descriptive Interpretation	
3.25 – 4.00	Extremely High Level	
2.50 – 3.24	High Level	
1.75 – 2.49	Low Level	
1.00 – 1.74	Extremely Low Level	

The current level of cultural leadership among teachers at Mercedes Elementary School in terms of instructional practices is extremely high level, with an average weighted mean of 3.27 while the sub-indicator concerning in collaborating with colleagues to develop interdisciplinary projects that emphasize cultural relevance, and integration had the least weighted mean of 3.14 as high level. This indicates a strong level of cultural leadership among teachers at Mercedes Elementary School, particularly in integrating cultural diversity into the curriculum. However, while collaboration with colleagues to develop interdisciplinary projects focusing on cultural integration was also rated highly, it reveals an opportunity for further enhancement in collaborative efforts to strengthen the emphasis on cultural relevance.

The implications of these findings suggest opportunities for further enhancing cultural leadership among teachers at Mercedes Elementary School, particularly in terms of collaborative curriculum development. Teachers can leverage their existing strengths to ensure that lessons reflect learner diversity, fostering deeper interdisciplinary collaborations that emphasize cultural integration. The findings highlight the potential for creating a culturally enriched learning environment that not only celebrates the unique heritage of Mercedes, Camarines Norte, but also promotes inclusive educational experiences for all learners. The implications also suggest that sustained efforts to incorporate cultural diversity into the curriculum will contribute to a more inclusive and culturally responsive educational framework.

Several related studies conformed these valuable insights of cultural leadership in education. Birch (2023) exploration emphasizes how teachers can lead initiatives that integrate cultural elements into the curriculum, aligning with the focus on fostering cultural leadership at Mercedes Elementary School. Similarly, Petousi et al. (2022) study on interactive digital storytelling underscores the potential of technology to enhance cultural content integration, suggesting that both teachers and students can actively participate in creating culturally enriching learning experiences.

Table 3

Current Level of Cultural Leadership among Teachers at Mercedes Elementary School in Terms of Assessment Techniques

Assessments Techniques	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
I incorporate culturally themed projects and presentations as assessment tools, allowing students to showcase their understanding of local culture and heritage.	3.20	High Level
I utilize culturally inclusive questioning techniques during assessments, ensuring that questions reflect the diversity of students' backgrounds, including those from Mercedes, Camarines Norte.	3.28	Extremely High Level
I design performance assessments that allow students to apply cultural knowledge and perspectives to real-world scenarios relevant to their lives in Mercedes, Camarines Norte.	3.22	High Level
I integrate portfolio assessments that encourage students to curate artifacts representing their cultural identities and learning experiences within the context of Mercedes, Camarines Norte.	2.87	High Level
I implement peer and self-assessment protocols that promote cultural awareness and appreciation among students, fostering a collaborative learning environment enriched by diverse perspectives.	3.15	High Level
Overall Weighted Mean	3.14	High Level

Rating Scale	Descriptive Interpretation
3.25 – 4.00	Extremely High Level
2.50 – 3.24	High Level
1.75 – 2.49	Low Level
1.00 – 1.74	Extremely Low Level

The current level of cultural leadership among teachers at Mercedes Elementary School in terms of assessment techniques is high level, with an average weighted mean of 3.14 while the sub-indicator concerning in integrating portfolio assessments that encourage students to curate artifacts representing their cultural identities and learning

experiences within the context of Mercedes, Camarines Norte had the least weighted mean of 2.87 as high level.

The implications of these findings suggest significant opportunities for enhancing cultural leadership among teachers at Mercedes Elementary School, particularly in terms of assessment techniques. Teachers' existing strengths in utilizing culturally inclusive questioning techniques indicate potential for further refining assessment practices to better reflect the diversity of learners' backgrounds. The findings highlight the importance of fostering cultural competency among educators to ensure assessments authentically capture students' varied experiences and perspectives. By addressing these areas, Mercedes Elementary School can strengthen its commitment to fostering a culturally responsive learning environment that promotes equity, inclusion, and academic success for all learners.

The findings of the study corroborated by Dizon (2020), who conducted a content analysis of K to 12 World History teaching guides, emphasizing the importance of balanced teaching approaches to foster various historical thinking skills among Grade the students.

Table 4

Current Level of Cultural Leadership among Teachers at Mercedes Elementary School in terms of Resource Acquisition

Resource Acquisition	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
I actively seek out and acquire culturally diverse teaching materials and resources that reflect the backgrounds of my students, including those from Mercedes, and Camarines Norte.	3.13	High Level
I collaborate with local community organizations and cultural institutions to acquire resources that enhance cultural learning experiences for students.	2.94	High Level
I raise funds to purchase resources towards the procurement of materials and resources that support the integration of local culture and heritage into the curriculum.	2.50	High Level
I engage in professional development opportunities to expand my knowledge and understanding of culturally relevant teaching resources and how to acquire them effectively.	3.28	Extremely High Level

I leverage technology and online platforms to access a wide range of culturally diverse resources and materials for classroom use, supplementing traditional resources.	3.11	High Level
Overall Weighted Mean	2.99	High Level
Rating Scale	Descriptive Interpretation	
3.25 – 4.00	Extremely High Level	
2.50 – 3.24	High Level	
1.75 – 2.49	Low Level	
1.00 – 1.74	Extremely Low Level	

The current level of cultural leadership among teachers at Mercedes Elementary School in terms of resource acquisition. The indicator “I engage in professional development opportunities to expand my knowledge and understanding of culturally relevant teaching resources and how to acquire them effectively.” received the highest weighted mean of 3.28, interpreted as extremely high level, while the indicator “I raise funds to purchase resources towards the procurement of materials and resources that support the integration of local culture and heritage into the curriculum.” received the lowest weighted mean of 2.50, interpreted as high level. In general, the current level of cultural leadership among teachers at Mercedes Elementary School in terms of resource acquisition is high level, with an average weighted mean of 2.99.

Interpreting the findings, the overall high level of cultural leadership in resource acquisition reflects teachers' commitment to seeking out and utilizing culturally relevant teaching resources to enrich the learning experiences of their students. By engaging in professional development opportunities, teachers demonstrate a willingness to invest in their learning and development to better serve the diverse needs of their learners. However, the need to increase efforts in fundraising for resources indicates a potential opportunity for teachers to explore additional avenues for acquiring materials that support the integration of local culture and heritage into the curriculum.

This result conformed by Amores (2015) study, which emphasizes the value of tracing local history through object biographies, providing insights into the acquisition of tangible artifacts that connect with students’ cultural backgrounds.

Table 5

Level Integration of Educational Materials and Resources for Teaching the Local History of Mercedes, Camarines Norte

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
I effectively integrate diverse educational materials, such as visual aids and multimedia resources, to enhance the understanding of local history among my pupils.	3.26	Extremely High Level

I consistently incorporate relevant local artifacts and primary sources into my teaching to provide authentic historical context.	2.91	High Level
I actively seek and utilize educational materials that reflect the cultural diversity of Mercedes, Camarines Norte in my history lessons.	3.09	High Level
I assess the adequacy of available resources to ensure comprehensive coverage of the local history curriculum.	3.06	High Level
I adapt and modify educational materials to suit the unique learning needs and preferences of my pupils.	3.13	High Level
I collaborate with colleagues to share and exchange educational resources for local history instruction.	3.06	High Level
I regularly update and refresh the pool of educational materials used in teaching local history to maintain relevance.	2.93	High Level
I employ technology, such as digital archives and online resources, to supplement traditional educational materials for a more dynamic learning experience.	3.17	High Level
I encourage pupils to actively engage with educational materials, fostering a sense of curiosity and exploration.	3.28	Extremely High Level
I assess the effectiveness of integrated educational materials through feedback and reflection, making adjustments as needed for continuous improvement.	3.17	High-Level
Overall Weighted Mean	3.10	High Level
Rating Scale	Descriptive Interpretation	
3.25 – 4.00	Extremely High Level	
2.50 – 3.24	High Level	
1.75 – 2.49	Low Level	
1.00 – 1.74	Extremely Low Level	

Interpreting these findings, the overall average weighted mean of 3.10 reflects a generally high level of integration of educational materials and resources for teaching local history at Mercedes Elementary School. While certain aspects, such as encouraging

active engagement, demonstrate exceptional performance, there remains room for enhancement in maintaining the currency and relevance of educational materials. This balanced assessment underscores the school's strengths in fostering learner engagement while also identifying opportunities for growth in resource management and curriculum development practices.

The implications of these findings are twofold. Firstly, the findings highlight importance of continuing to prioritize strategies that promote active engagement with educational materials among learners. This underscores the need for maintaining and enhancing integration of educational materials in teaching the local history of Mercedes, Camarines Norte. Secondly, the findings suggest that improving digital instructional materials, specifically, video lessons or interactive video presentation is crucial for ensuring learners have access to timely and relevant content. This indicates the necessity for mechanisms that support the ongoing review and renewal of materials, as well as collaboration with local organizations or experts to introduce diverse perspectives and resources into the curriculum. Addressing these implications can contribute to sustaining a high level of integration of educational materials and resources for teaching local history of Mercedes, Camarines Norte ultimately enriching the learning experiences of students at Mercedes Elementary School.

In addressing the implications of prioritizing learner engagement with educational materials and enhancing the regular updating of resources at Mercedes Elementary School, it is supported with the insights from related studies on effective strategies. Bual and Alec (2021) examine best practices and challenges among higher education institutions in Philippine history course reviews, offering valuable perspectives on maintaining the relevance of educational resources. This study underscores the importance of establishing mechanisms for ongoing review and renewal of materials, aligning with the school's goal of ensuring timely and pertinent content for learners.

Additionally, Guiliano (2022) supported this as it presents innovative method for refreshing resources through technology integration, as seen in the primer for teaching digital history. By leveraging digital tools and augmented reality, teachers can provide dynamic and interactive learning experiences that enrich learners' connections with local history. These studies offer practical insights that Mercedes Elementary School can leverage to address the implications and enhance the integration of educational materials, ultimately enriching learners' learning experiences in local history education.

Table 6

Challenges Teachers Faced when Localizing and Contextualizing the History

Indicators	Frequency	Ranking
Difficulty in accessing relevant and accurate local historical resources for teaching purposes.	24	6.5
Insufficient training or professional development opportunities on effective localization and contextualization strategies.	29	4

Limited availability of technology or educational tools to enhance the teaching of local history.	32	2
Resistance or lack of interest among students towards the local history of Mercedes, Camarines Norte.	19	12
Challenges in aligning the local history curriculum with broader educational standards.	19	12
Inadequate support from school administration in promoting and prioritizing local history education.	9	20
Time constraints within the curriculum to dedicate sufficient attention to local history.	34	1
Lack of collaboration and knowledge-sharing among teachers regarding successful localization practices.	16	15.5
Cultural diversity among students requires varied instructional approaches to ensure inclusivity.	14	17.5
Limited community involvement or partnerships to enrich the contextualization of local history lessons.	30	3
Development of culturally responsive lesson plans and teaching guides for local history topics.	16	15.5
Creation of visually engaging multimedia resources, such as videos and presentations, to supplement lessons.	22	8
Designing interactive learning modules that incorporate local cultural elements into various subjects.	19	12
Establishment of a centralized digital repository with easy access to a diverse range of comprehensive local history materials.	20	10
Collaboration with local artists to produce visually appealing and culturally relevant educational materials.	21	9
Incorporation of local history narratives into existing textbooks and educational resources.	24	6.5
Provision of funding for teachers to attend workshops on creating culturally inclusive instructional materials.	28	5
Development of digital platforms for sharing and accessing culturally enriched teaching resources.	18	14
Integration of local history storytelling techniques into classroom activities and assessments.	10	19
Regular updates and enhancements to instructional materials based on teacher and student feedback.	14	17.5

Table 6 presents the challenges teachers faced when localizing and contextualizing the history. The top 3 highest in frequency were: "Time constraints within the curriculum to dedicate sufficient attention to local history" (f=34), "Limited availability of technology or educational tools to enhance the teaching of local history" (f=32), and "Limited community involvement or partnerships to enrich the contextualization of local history lessons" (f=30).

The implications of these findings reveal significant challenges for teachers in Mercedes, Camarines Norte, in localizing and contextualizing local history. Time constraints and limited resources, including technology and community partnerships, highlight systemic issues that affect the integration of local history into the curriculum. These challenges illustrate the broader systemic issues within educational structures that impact how effectively local history can be taught.

To further support the findings, the study by Caingcoy et al. (2022) emphasize the importance of assessing teachers' culturally responsive teaching. Their research providing educators with adequate support and resources to effectively integrate diverse educational materials. Both studies reinforce the idea that empowering teachers through professional development and resource acquisition initiatives is crucial for fostering a cultural teaching environment, which aligns with the present study's results on the significant role of cultural leadership in enhancing teaching practices.

Table 7

Relationship Between the Cultural Leadership of Teachers and the Level of Integration of Instructional Material or Resources

Level of Integration of Educational Materials/ Resources	Instructional Practices		Cultural Integration		Assessment Techniques		Resource Acquisition	
	r	p-value	r	p-value	r	p-value	r	p-value
	0.423**	0.001	0.619**	0.00	0.516**	0.00	0.607**	0.00

***Correlation is significant @.01 level*

The level of integration of instructional material or resources and instructional practices actively involve students in discussions that promote cultural understanding and appreciation of Mercedes, Camarines Norte. Likewise, the level of cultural leadership of teachers and their level of cultural integration in teaching ensures that lessons reflect the diversity of students' backgrounds and experiences, including those from Mercedes, Camarines Norte. Moreover, the level of integration of educational materials or resources and the level of cultural leadership on assessment and technique utilized culturally inclusive questioning techniques during assessments, ensuring that questions reflect the diversity of students' backgrounds, including those from Mercedes, Camarines Norte. Finally, the level of cultural leadership of teachers along with resource acquisition and their level of integration of educational materials or resources engage in professional development opportunities to expand the knowledge and understanding of culturally relevant teaching resources and how to acquire them effectively.

The implications of these findings highlight the critical role of fostering cultural leadership among teachers to improve the integration of educational materials for teaching local history. The data suggest that teachers with higher levels of cultural leadership are more effective in incorporating cultural elements into their teaching practices, which enhances students' engagement and understanding of local history. This underscores the potential benefits of investing in programs that develop teachers' cultural leadership skills, which can lead to more culturally responsive educational practices and enrich students' learning experiences. Such investment not only promotes a deeper appreciation of local history but also fosters a more inclusive and equitable learning environment that reflects the diverse cultural backgrounds of students.

To further support the findings, the study by Caingcoy et al. (2022) emphasize the importance of assessing practice teachers' culturally responsive teaching. The research highlights the necessity of providing educators with adequate support and resources to effectively integrate diverse educational materials. It reinforces the idea that empowering teachers through professional development and resource acquisition initiatives is crucial for fostering a culturally aware teaching environment, which aligns with the present study's results on the significant role of cultural leadership in enhancing teaching practices.

Conclusions

Based on the obtained results, the researcher formulated the following conclusions:

1. The level of cultural leadership among teachers at Mercedes Elementary School is generally high. Teachers demonstrate an extremely high level of cultural leadership in both instructional practices and curricular integration, reflecting strong efforts to incorporate cultural elements into their teaching. While the level of cultural leadership in assessment techniques and resource acquisition is also high, these areas offer opportunities for further improvement. The findings suggest that teachers are effectively fostering a culturally responsive learning environment, with potential for continued growth in certain aspects.

2. The integration of educational materials and resources for teaching the local history of Mercedes, Camarines Norte is high. This indicates that teachers are effectively incorporating relevant materials into their lessons to enhance students' understanding of local history. The high level of integration reflects a strong commitment to making local cultural content accessible and engaging for learners. However, maintaining this level of integration will require continuous efforts to source and develop diverse and relevant materials that can further enrich the teaching of local history.

3. Teachers face notable challenges when localizing and contextualizing the history of Mercedes, Camarines Norte in their lessons. The primary issues include time constraints within the curriculum that limit the opportunity to thoroughly address local history, insufficient availability of technology and educational tools to enhance teaching, and a lack of community involvement or partnerships that could enrich lesson contextualization. Addressing these challenges is crucial for improving the effectiveness of local history education.

4. Teachers who demonstrate stronger cultural leadership skills are more inclined to integrate cultural elements effectively into their teaching materials and resources. Such integration enhances the richness and authenticity of the educational experience, fostering a deeper understanding and appreciation of local history among students.

5. The Digital Instructional Material represents a significant step toward enhancing the cultural leadership skills of teachers in Mercedes, Camarines Norte. By providing

comprehensive support and intervention, the Digital Instructional Material equips educators with the necessary tool to integrate local history and culture into their teaching practices effectively. The initiative promotes inclusive educational experiences that celebrate the community's rich cultural heritage, fostering a learning environment where cultural diversity is valued.

Recommendations

Considering the findings and conclusions, recommendations for possible actions are made.

1. Resource acquisition may be strengthened by building partnerships with local communities and cultural organizations to provide access to more culturally relevant materials. This recommendation directly addresses the identified gap in resource acquisition.

2. Professional development programs that focus on enhancing culturally responsive assessment strategies may be conducted, which aligns with the need to improve assessment techniques in cultural leadership.

3. Sourcing more diverse and locally relevant materials may be prioritized, along with providing professional development to equip teachers with strategies for effectively utilizing these resources. This may align with the need for better integration of local history into teaching.

4. Teachers may be encouraged to strengthen their cultural leadership skills through targeted professional development programs. By enhancing these skills, teachers are more likely to integrate cultural elements effectively into their teaching materials and resources. This integration may enrich the educational experience, fostering a deeper understanding and appreciation of local history among learners, and promoting a more culturally responsive learning environment.

5. Clear guidelines and action plans may be proposed for implementing the Digital Instructional Material, ensuring it may become an effective tool for promoting cultural leadership. This may align with the goal of improving cultural leadership in the school.

6. In future studies, the developed instructional materials can be utilized, tested and evaluated by both learners and teachers to test the effectiveness. It should consider conducting follow-up assessments to determine if the intervention has a lasting effect. Improvements can be made based on the result of the study.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The author gave great importance to ethical considerations, ensuring that respondents are thoroughly informed about the project's goals and the use of its results by gaining informed permission. Respondents had the freedom to choose whether to participate, with the guarantee that their decision to leave did not have a negative impact

on their involvement in the program or their relationship with the researcher or affiliated research organizations. Respondents are not required to submit reasons for withdrawal, which promoted dedication to voluntary and ethical participation in research. The ethical standards protocol for this study included ensuring informed consent, maintaining confidentiality and anonymity of respondents' data, obtaining explicit permission to record responses, acknowledging respondents' right to withdraw from the study without providing a reason, respecting their right to refuse to answer sensitive questions, and affirming their right to ask questions. In addition, the study actively pursued ethical approval from the SDO CN-Schools Division Superintendent, and it consistently prioritized the values of honesty, transparency, and the safety of respondents. The author upheld the utmost ethical standards throughout the research process, consistently monitoring ethical concerns, and offering debriefings as needed.

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